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The Power of the Family: New Data Reveal the Role of the Historical Family as the In- stigator of Disparate and Lasting Developmental Trajectories

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ABSTRACT

Recent years have witnessed a growing interest in the role of the historical family as the instigator of disparate developmental trajectories. However, more work is needed to underpin these findings within comprehensive and robust data quality frameworks. Using a novel historical database of the European family we show that countries starting out from more patriarchal family structures in the past exhibit more hierarchical gender relations, more collectivist mindsets, and lower levels of economic and human development today. Given the irreversibility of these relationships, we argue that historical family patterns set countries on vicious-vs.-virtuous trajectories leading to divergent developmental outcomes today.

Key words: family systems - comparative development – patriarchy - historical persistence

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The Power of the Family:

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INTRODUCTION

Over the past few years historical family organization has become the object of extensive research in economics and cross-cultural studies as part of a broader agenda on the impact of culture on economic performance and comparative development (e.g., Greif 2006; Duranton et al. 2009; De Moor and Van Zanden 2010; Foreman-Peck 2011; Carmichael et al. 2016a; Rijpma and Carmichael 2016; Carmichael and Rijpma 2017; Dennison and Ogilvie 2014, 2016; Dilli 2017; Le Bris 2016; Szołtysek et al. 2017a; Santos Silva et al. 2017; Bertocchi and Bozzano 2015; also Alexander and Welzel 2015). By reversing the more usual view according to which the family has been a relatively passive unit affected by exogenous “superstructures”, this perspective posits that linkages between family systems and various societal domains might have also run in the opposite direction, i.e. from the family as the cellular core of any human community, to this community’s larger social aggregations, from local assemblies to regional associations to nation states. From this bottom-up perspective of social formation, it is plausible to assume that the axial principles of family and household organization—such as the question of whether the unit is formed by coercion or consent, or whether it is based on hierarchy or equality—spill over to higher levels of organization as societies evolve. Furthermore, given that many contemporary regional differences have deep historical roots (Spolaore and Wacziarg 2013); persistent familial traits are likely to cast a very long shadow on recent cross-country differences in value orientations and developmental outcomes.

This new emerging literature has already provoked a considerable amount of controversy, involving debates on the precise underlying mechanisms, the role of non-familial institutions and the possibility of reversed causality (Dennison and Ogilvie 2014, 2016; Carmichael et al. 2016b), as well as on the possibility of placing over-excessive focus on the distinction between presumably “unique” demographic regimes of the North Atlantic seaboard and the rest of Europe (Szołtysek et al. 2017a).

Another recurring problem encountered in all previous studies was that they had to work around a lack of reliable historical data. The consequent reliance on the “cultural ideal” family types rather than on the actual past familial behavior has resulted in linking the developmental statistics to crude classifications of historical family systems, the spatial and multidimensional nature of which were considered only selectively. Furthermore, the postulated historicity of family patterns was more often taken for granted rather than explicitly tested. In the face of these multiple challenges, Carmichael and coauthors (2016b, 200) recently suggested that the criticism of the family role in comparative development may well be premature, and should be re-examined using newly available historical demographic databases.

In this paper we make four distinct contributions to this debate by responding to Carmichael's plea. First, we demonstrate the usefulness of recent developments in historical microdata infrastructures (Ruggles 2012) by constructing a database of European family patterns over the last few hundred years using information from the Mosaic and the North Atlantic Population projects. Second, we apply a composite measure of familial organisation in historic Europe (the Patriarchy Index; henceforth PI) which allows for a multidimensional operationalization of historical family systems to the extent which has not been accomplished before. This measure, which builds on observable societal characteristics derived from a massive repository of historical microdata, is used through a bottom-up aggregation to yield historical patriarchy scores for 26 contemporary European countries. Third, by linking these patriarchy traits to a number of contemporary indicators we expand the on-going debate by testing the relationship between historical family patterns and contemporary gender inequality, value orientations, economic growth and human development in a unified empirical framework.¹ Finally, we provide the first systematic verification of the thesis on the long-term persistence of the cross-country family traits across the continent, which is central to the debate in question.

The main finding of this paper is that historical family organization is associated with developmental and value disparities among European nations today. Using cross-country correlations (bivariate) and multivariate regressions, we show that countries starting out from more patriarchal family structures in the past exhibit more hierarchical gender relations, more collectivist mindsets, and lower levels of economic and human development today. Given a strong and robust correlation between several independent accounts of familial behavior today and family patterns in the past which we unravel, we take this evidence as suggesting that the correlation is more likely to run from family patterns to developmental outcomes, i.e. that indeed family patterns in the past set countries on vicious-vs.-virtuous trajectories leading to divergent developmental outcomes today.

Overall, our systematic analysis extends previous dispersed findings on the role of historical family organisation in explaining developmental gradients in Europe, and provides strong incentives for continued research efforts along these lines. Our findings also dovetail with the expanding literature seeking the origins of contemporary differences in values and beliefs by stressing the role of family as the fundamental source of many crucial cognitive, behavioral and cultural traits which – projected into the future – may exert a long-lasting impact on contemporary value orientations (Bisin and Verdier 2001; Alesina and Giuliano 2014; Santos Silva et al. 2017). Last, but not least, our paper highlights the power of family and economic history working together to provide more comprehensive and robust methodological and data quality frameworks to test relationships between various societal domains.

¹ The narrowing of our view to Europe is dictated by the scope of the datasets we employ. At the same time, using bigger lens to observe a smaller number of potentially less-variable countries may be beneficial to spotting issues which may escape attention at a truly global scale, where even microscopic differences can turn out to be statistically significant. Also, Emmanuel Todd's pioneering work (see below) has started with Europe.

The remaining of this paper is divided into six parts. First, we review the state of research exploring how historical family patterns are linked to current developmental outcomes and discuss problems associated with these earlier approaches. We then present our own data, measures and methodologies. In the core parts of the paper, we examine degrees of covariation between our historical country-level indicators of family organization and selected contemporary indicators, using both correlational and multivariate framework. We complement these sections with an assessment of the robustness of our regression results. The penultimate section discusses main causal paths that could account for the observed associations and provides evidence for the persistence of historical family patterns to the present. We conclude by summarizing our findings and suggesting some research agendas for the future.

PREVIOUS LITERATURE

The notion that family systems could have had an impact on wider societal outcomes has a long pedigree. For example, Max Weber alluded to it when he argued that strong family values do not allow for the development of individual forms of entrepreneurship, which are fundamental to the formation of capitalist societies (Weber 1904; also Banfield 1958; Nimkoff 1965, 61 ff). In the last few years, these ideas have regained prominence in New Institutional Economics after scholars have re-discovered the importance of micro-level institutions at the grassroots of society such as family, from which macro-level institutions evolve through mechanisms of bottom-up aggregation (see Alesina and Giuliano 2010; earlier Sen 1983). Intuitively, families and households are likely to be primary agents in the process of human capital formation, value orientations and in shaping economic behaviors, especially in societies that lacked widespread schooling and formal educational institutions. The realm of the family is not only the area where people make many decisions (Sen 1983), families and households are also the key arena for building and enacting kinship ties, for socializing individuals, and for transmitting values, including values related to power and equality, justice and gender, age hierarchy, and the relationship between the individual and the authorities (e.g., Mason 2001; Carmichael et al. 2016a; Kok 2017; Mamadouh 1999).

The ideas about the role the contemporary family plays in shaping economic behavior and attitudes have been tested by Alberto Alesina and Paola Giuliano (2010, 2014). Using a worldwide dataset they analyzed the relationship between the strength of family values and four different types of societal attitudes conducive to higher productivity and growth. They found that, on average, familistic values are associated with lower political participation and political action. They are also related to a lower level of trust, more emphasis on job security, less desire for innovation, and more traditional attitudes toward working women.²

² Earlier, Bertrand and Schoar (2006) documented the systematic correlations between the strength of family ties and economic outcomes, showing that present-day countries with strong family ties have lower economic development on average (e.g., lower levels of per capita GDP). For evidence suggesting that strong family ties are not that unambiguously

The possibility that family ties could influence contemporary European social, economic and ideational spheres via their distant origins soon appeared on the horizon (Greif 2006; Therborn 2004; earlier Reher 1998). Reher (1998), for example, suggested that geographically distinct family patterns in Europe, rooted in deep preindustrial past, have implications for the way different societies function today. Tine De Moor and Jan Luiten Van Zanden (2010; also Greif 2006; Foreman-Peck 2011) re-introduced earlier suggestions of Peter Laslett (and others) by positing that the historical north-western European marriage and family pattern (based on late marriage, neolocality, and high levels of lifetime celibacy among women; henceforth EMP) was a key factor not only in the economic success of northern and western Europe relative to southern and eastern Europe, but also in the “great divergence” between Europe and the rest of the world.

However, such propositions have stumbled upon the major difficulty of finding historical data that would be both detailed and global to empirically anchor them. Although historical family has been at the center of scholarly interest for generations of scholars, the efforts undertaken until the recent outbreaks of digital microdata revolution have not resulted in data infrastructures that would allow for an omnibus empirical reconstruction of historical family patterns in Europe, not to mention those from beyond it. A way out of that conundrum was pursued by taking recourse to a world-wide classification of family systems inferred from anthropological evidence by Emmanuel Todd. Todd (1985, 1987) divided all countries of the world on the basis of three indicators, combinations of which he argued make up a family system: the practice of living in complex or nuclear households, whether cousin marriage is practiced, and whether there is partible inheritance between brothers. By combining these indicators, he developed strict categories and used them to distinguish four major types of family organization at the country level: the exogamous communitarian family, the authoritarian family, the egalitarian nuclear family, and the absolute nuclear family, all showcasing deep historical roots in their geographical distribution dating back to medieval times. He then embarked on a visual comparison between his map of historical family structures and a series of economic, political, and social maps of Europe, arguing that different patterns of family organization explain the diffusion of, or resistance to, a wide array of critical social changes on the continent, including the spread of Protestantism, secularism, and the acceptance and diffusion of communism.

Over the last ten years or so, Todd’s classification has been subjected to immense data “snooping”. Duranton and coauthors (2009) identified a significant association between Todd’s classification of family types and regional disparities in educational attainment, social capital, labour participation, wealth, and inequality in Western Europe. Le Bris (2016) built the family score based on Todd’s three family characteristics and found it to be significantly (and robustly) associated with contemporary variation in economic outcomes as measured by GDP across 79 countries of the world. Building further upon this evidence, Sarah Carmichael and colleagues used a combination of Todd’s clas-

antagonistic to development, progress and civic virtues, see for example Macry (1997), Whyte (1996) or Greenhalgh (1990).

sification with information compiled in George Murdock's *Ethnographic Atlas*³, to test the supposedly considerable influence the family patterns could have exerted on regional inequalities through their divergent impact on the status of women. In a series of analyses they found historical family constraints on female autonomy to be significantly and inversely associated with gender equality outcomes in contemporary world data (Rijpma and Carmichael 2016, 38; Carmichael and Rijpma 2017). They also established a strong and positive effect of "female friendly" family systems on the historical and contemporary estimates of per capita GDP for a range (25 to 52) of Eurasian countries. These analyses were complemented by Dilli (2017) who, relying on the same data, found that historical family institutions associated with higher female agency (such as equal inheritance practices, prevalence of nuclear household, late female marriage and the absence of polygamy) were related to higher levels of economic development across 92 contemporary countries.

While the prevalent reliance on Todd has been commonly justified as resulting from the lack of detailed but broad historical empirical data (e.g., Rijpma and Carmichael 2016), the weaknesses of this approach must be clearly acknowledged. For all its undeniable attractiveness (such as its apparently global hatch), Todd's classification displays severe deficiencies including the uncertainty about the empirical sources of his reconstructions, misleading classification of some countries, putting a premium on the "cultural ideal" rather than actual practice in family behaviors and its variation (particularly in Eastern Europe), and highly problematic projection of such "family systems" back in the distant past (earlier, see Greenhalgh 1987). Given these problems, recent inventive attempts to formalize Todd's scheme, too, run the danger of being not quite accurate representations of historical family organization (see extended discussion in Szołtysek and Poniak 2018).⁴

Due to obvious data limitations they had to work around, the previous approaches were inevitably vexed by important conceptual and methodological problems. Most importantly, because of the reliance on Todd's scheme the multidimensional nature of historical family systems could be considered only selectively. Of the many elements of family organisation that ought to be linked to economic performance and value orientation, only a few have been analyzed, with most researches focusing exclusively on household structure, some aspects of marriage, and inheritance. At the same time, several other elements of familial behavior, such as living as non-kin or life-cycle servants, age at marriage, headship and seniority patterns, as well as female position in domestic organization, which have long been used by historical demographers as major measurement yardsticks to distinguish between different family systems (e.g., Hajnal 1982), were impossible to examine. Also troublesome in this regard is a habitual reliance on cross-national or inter-regional comparisons of the proportions of households that were

³ Given the latter's meager coverage of Europe, the European part of their dataset was still based primarily on Todd.

⁴ As far as Europe is concerned, combining Todd's information with Murdock's "Ethnographic Atlas" – as Carmichael and coauthors have done – is largely irrelevant due to the latter's very poor coverage of the continent.

either nuclear or complex (Todd, Le Bris, Duranton, Dilli, Ogilvie and Dennison; also Greif), which errs in ignoring the fact that such measurements are highly sensitive to demographic conditions and therefore inappropriate for a comparative analysis of populations with substantially differing demographic behaviors (e.g., Ruggles 2012; King and Preston 1990)⁵. Finally, attempts at imposing a collective familial identity on entire populations, such as in Greif's account of the "Western European social organization" based on the nuclear family, or Dilli's belief in establishing a "dominant" household pattern in a given country, are equally perfunctory and run counter to both historical imagination and evidence (e.g., Szołtysek 2015).⁶

Furthermore, the postulated historicity of family patterns was more often taken for granted rather than explicitly tested. Neither Todd's own work, nor papers by Greif, De Moor and Van Zanden, and Duranton and co-authors, provided any empirical tests of these potential trajectories. While Duranton just conjectured the long-term persistence of medieval family types (Duranton et al. 2009), Rijpma and Carmichael observed that while their measures of historical family have some predictive power for today's measures of family characteristics, they are far from perfect (Rijpma and Carmichael 2016, 35).

This cursory survey of issues related to indicators of historical family systems currently employed for modelling the relationship between past familial structures and contemporary development demonstrates that there is potentially much to be gained from considering other classification systems. To the extent that such measures could be developed they might help to unravel new associations between past and present. In what follows we elucidate what such studies on the family-development nexus could aim for are they to capitalize on previously unavailable historical-demographic data.

DATA AND MEASURES

In order to provide more comprehensive data quality frameworks for the area of interest we drew on digital information revolution in family history which has recently produced an explosion in the availability of individual-level historical population data (Ruggles 2012). Our contribution builds on two such exemplary datasets recently made available: the combined North Atlantic Population Project (NAPP) and Mosaic databases of historical census microdata (Ruggles et al. 2011; Szołtysek and Gruber 2016; Szołtysek et al. 2017b). These data are broadly available in the form of machine-readable, harmonized microdata samples derived from various kinds of historical census and census-like materials, including full-count national censuses, as well as local fragments of censuses, church lists of parishioners, tax lists, local estate inventories, all of

⁵ According to Ruggles, "the percentage of complex households tells us virtually nothing about the family system" (2012, 431).

⁶ The approach of Dennison and Ogilvie (2014, 2016) who used a meta-dataset of historical marriage and household patterns in 33 European countries derived from 365 research studies, falls victim to generally the same caveats, while at the same time casting reservations about the coverage and the integrity of the data (see Carmichael et al. 2016b).

which are very similar in terms of structure, organisation, and the types of information they provide.⁷ Anchored at the micro-level, these data allow for the unravelling of large-scale demographic patterns through a bottom-up aggregation of individual- and household-level characteristics and the generation of historical localized familial and demographic indicators across multiple locations, and at different scales.

Mosaic currently includes 142 machine-readable samples of historical census and census-like microdata. It stretches over a large area of continental Europe from Catalonia to the Urals, between 1700 and 1918, and includes individual records for 1.1 million (1,085,136) persons living in 208,939 family households. NAPP expands the collection towards Great Britain and Scandinavia, bringing in data for additional 151 historical regions from five national censuses with more than 14 million observations. Whereas Mosaic samples are of a varying level of representativeness (see Szołtysek and Gruber 2016)⁸, the NAPP components stand either for full-count census data or representative samples taken from them⁹. Altogether the combined database includes 293 regional populations, with 15.3 million persons living in 3 million households, outweighing in its scope and content all precedent infrastructure efforts in family history. Of the 293 regional datasets, a slight majority (56%) represents populations after 1850, while 44% cover populations before 1850, and 21% populations before 1800. The collection includes information on both rural and urban sites, although rural societies predominate (see Figure 1; also Appendix: Section II).

⁷ See www.censusmosaic.org; <https://www.nappdata.org/napp/>. All of the samples describe the characteristics of individuals in a given settlement or area grouped into households (co-resident domestic groups), and provide information on the relationships between co-resident individuals, as well as their sex, age, and marital status.

⁸ Even though the Mosaic data are based on various sampling schemes (which are in turn contingent upon data availability), they cannot be considered a probability sample of the historical European societies or of the cultures for which the Mosaic database provides information.

⁹ In collecting the NAPP data we gave preference to the oldest available censuses for north-western Europe. It was possible to obtain data for Iceland, Denmark, and Norway for the late 18th/early 19th centuries; while for Sweden (1880) and England and Wales (1881) we were forced to use NAPP data from the late 19th century (the data for Great Britain in 1851 were highly clustered, and were therefore not considered). Except in England, where we employed a 10-percent sample, we used 100-percent samples. All of the other data from Great Britain represent 100-percent samples.

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of the combined Mosaic/NAPP data.

Notes: for sources of the Mosaic and NAPP data, see Appendix: Section III

Using a range of harmonized variables from Mosaic and NAPP, a composite measure of historical family organization known as the Patriarchy Index was computed, reflecting varying degrees of sex- and age-related social inequality across different family settings. The index combines ten variables grouped in four “domains” – the domination of men over women, the domination of the older generation over the younger generation, the extent of patrilocality, and the preference for sons. Table 1 provides the complete list of the ten components, showing how they are defined and measured, and indicating the expected direction of their relationship with familial patriarchy levels (+/-) (more in Gruber and Szoltysek 2016; Szoltysek et al. 2017b). Most of the component variables directly capture various forms of gender and generational biases at the household level. Other variables proxy behavioral patterns that could not be derived directly from our data; for example, patrilocality partially accounts for otherwise unobservable inheritance practices, while the proportion of young females living as non-kin can be interpreted as a distant relative to the female labour force participation measures under the preindustrial conditions.

Table 1. Components of the Patriarchy Index – following page.

Domain / Component	Component	Abbreviation	Definition / Measurement	Relationship with patriarchy	Specification
Male domination	Proportion of female household head	<i>Female heads</i>	The proportion of all female household heads among all adult (20+) household heads of family households	Negative	Age-standardized
	Proportion of young brides	<i>Young brides</i>	The proportion of ever-married women in the age group 15-19 years	Positive	
	Proportion of wives who are older than their husbands	<i>Older wives</i>	The proportion of all of the wives who are older than their husbands among all of the couples for whom the ages of both partners are known	Negative	Age-standardized
	Proportion of young women living as non-kin	<i>Female non-kin</i>	The proportion of elderly people (aged 65+) living with at least one lateral relative in the household	Positive	Age-standardized
Generational domination	Proportion of elderly men coresiding with a younger household head	<i>Younger household head</i>	The proportion of elderly men (aged 65+ years) living in a household headed by a male household head of a younger generation	Negative	Only family households; the elderly men must be relatives of the household head
	Proportion of neolocal residence among young men	<i>Neolocal</i>	The proportion of male household heads living without any relatives except spouses and children among ever-married men in the age group 20-29 years	Negative	Only family households; age-standardized
	Proportion of elderly people living with lateral relatives	<i>Lateral</i>	The proportion of elderly people (aged 65+) living with at least one lateral relative in the household	Positive	Only family households
Patrilocality	Proportion of elderly people living with married daughters	<i>Married daughter</i>	The proportion of elderly people (aged 65+) living with at least one married daughter in the same household among those elderly people who live with at least one married child in the same household	Negative	Only family households
Son preference	Proportion of boys among the last child	<i>Boy as last child</i>	The proportion of boys among the last children (if the last child is one of a set of siblings of both sexes, he or she will be excluded from the analysis).	Positive	Only children of household heads; only age group 10 to 14 years; family households
	Sex ratio of youngest age group	<i>Sex ratio</i>	The sex ratio (boys to 100 girls) in the youngest age group (0-4 years old)	Positive	Only family households

These components are molded into a composite measure constructed on the basis of information contained in Mosaic and NAPP data and at the level of resolution of regions as presented in Figure 1 above.¹⁰ The PI can be said to characterize the situation of women, the aged, and young people according to the extent to which they had obtained socially valued resources (such as a desirable position or status), albeit without measuring the positions of these groups relative to certain normative standards or reference categories. The index values thus represent absolute, not relative, measures of gender and age inequality (Szołtysek et al. 2017b, 238). It has been shown that in the absence of comparative qualitative information PI can be used to account for the strength of familism and is a good measure of strong/weak family ties in historical populations (Szołtysek and Poniak 2018).

In order to be able to relate cross-country developmental measures to historical estimates of patriarchy, the latter were averaged for contemporary country borders and sat at the average time when their relevant information was taken from, making allowance for multiple boundary changes and population flows in the course of the 20th century wherever necessary. For the NAPP countries, we took an average PI value weighted by population size of their constituent regional groups.¹¹ The same strategy was applied to a number of countries represented in Mosaic with several censuses of the same structure (i.e., either rural or urban). Where contrary was the case, the average PI value from various censuses was weighted by an index of urbanization characteristic of a given area at a respective time-period using data available from Malanima (2010). In this way, the weight of the overrepresented urban populations could be mitigated in favor of the rural areas. In cases where our country values are derived from censuses of a different chronology, the above procedure was applied to each dataset separately, then followed by taking a grand mean (here, weights related to population size were no longer used). The only special case in this regard was that of Switzerland – for two periods the available populations were either rural or urban. Here, we still applied the urbanization weights (averaged for the periods in question) which enabled us to reduce the impact of a very low PI characterizing the 19th century Zurich. Finally, when it comes to countries for which there was only one census population available in Mosaic, the PI value derived from that population was taken to represent that whole country.

¹⁰ Cronbach's alpha for 10 components of the Index equals 0.87 (|0.85, 0.89|), suggesting that the items have relatively high internal consistency. The alpha coefficient of reliability also suggests that there is no component variable that would decrease the Index's general reliability. Principal Component Analysis shows that the ten components of the Index load on two dimensions which altogether explain nearly 70 percent of the variance. This confirms that the notion of family systems we are trying to capture is not unidimensional (see Schuerer 2015; Wall 1995). Because the construction of the Index was mainly theory-driven, the PCA results do not invalidate its composition.

¹¹ In what follows we focus primarily on the Mosaic part of the dataset which is used for that paper. Since the NAPP regional data are derived from complete populations or 10% representative samples or full census counts, they are of no issue in this regard.

In the end, following those routines we were able to compute the historical PI values for 26 contemporary European countries.¹² These values range from 12 to 29 index points, with Denmark scoring lowest on the patriarchy scale, and Albania situated at the top end of it (see Figure 2 and Table 2). The social prevalence of the PI may be taken to have variably influenced not only cultural orientation of a given society in the past, but also largely the types of action which dominate thereby, including those prone to more rigid gender and age hierarchies, and enactment of loyalty to family, kin or lineage, filial piety, reverence for ancestors and obedience; and in-group assortative sociality (cf. Vandello and Cohen 1999, 279).

Figure 2. Cross-country variation in historical patriarchy (combined Mosaic/NAPP data)

Notes: for sources of the Mosaic and NAPP data, see Appendix: Section III. Grey color indicates no data.

¹² Although this figure may appear quite small, it's worth noting that it still represents more than a half of current European countries. Our sample size can be placed at the bottom end of the sample size distributions that we have encountered in the output growth analyses, such as those of Levine and Zervos (1998; the N-range from 32 to 45 countries) or Knack and Keefer (1997; 29 countries). More recently, Santos Silva et al. (2017) presented regressions based on as low a number of countries as 25 (p.59); and Olsson and Paik (2013) regressions based on 21 to 31 observations (see tables 3 and 5-6).

Table 2. Basic characteristics of Mosaic/NAPP country samples

Country	PI	No. of populations	Size	% rural	Time (average)	Time (range)
Albania	29,32	14	140611	58	1918	–
Austria	14,9	4	20036	74	1910	–
Belarus	25,1	2	44508	100	1793	1768–1804
Belgium	14	1	13666	100	1814	–
Bulgaria	24,68	2	8373	78	1908	1877–1947
Croatia	22	1	1880	100	1674	–
Denmark	12,2	19	838623	94	1787	–
France	16,37	5	27745	79	1845	1831–1901
Germany	14,24	44	384049	62	1824	1700–1900
Hungary	19	4	13724	100	1869	–
Iceland	14	1	51003	100	1703	–
Lithuania	22,5	2	19917	100	1847	–
Netherlands	13,6	5	40037	53	1811	1810–1811
Norway	16,3	21	878073	95	1801	–
Poland	16,66	10	83276	65	1791	1666–1809
Romania	20,1	8	14514	100	1844	1781–1879
Russia	22,59	11	46296	92	1768	1710–1897
Slovakia	20,5	3	8410	100	1869	–
Spain	20,9	3	23997	29	1889	1880–1890
Sweden	12,9	24	4624825	92	1880	–
Ukraine	22,16	11	90022	81	1815	1765–1897
U.K.	11,6	83	7859626	57	1881	–
Serbia	24,73	3	19180	86	1870	1863–1884
Turkey	20	2	8354	0	1896	1885–1907
Switzerland	17,28	3	16140	68	1787	1671–1870
Latvia	19,1	4	35807	100	1797	–

Source: Mosaic and NAPP

Although the outcomes of our aggregation strategy may be subject to some limitations due to the unequal coverage of contemporary countries with the Mosaic data, the dataset advanced here can be cautiously considered as accounting for cross-country variation in historical family patterns, i.e., as representing country-level generalizations derived from empirically assessed variation at the local/regional level. To this end it is perhaps worth pointing out that except for Croatia, Bulgaria, Turkey and Spain (each represented by a single or highly clustered censal population; see Figure 1), the rest of our country means yield fairly reasonable representations of those countries' his-

torical familial diversity at a certain moment in time (Szołtysek and Gruber 2016).¹³ Controlling for time period in subsequent regression models also removes part of the evolution problem making it possible to account for variable effects of family systems captured at different times.

Furthermore, by combining a range of variables related to familial behavior rather than just focusing on marriage patterns or on the prevalence of nuclear families, the underlying structure of the PI represents an important step towards a truly multi-stranded account of family organization in the past (see Mason 2001, 160-161). By choosing to use individual-level age-specific measures instead of household level variables, as suggested by Ruggles, fears about the undesired influence of variation in demographic conditions on indicators of family structure can also be allayed. Moreover, by capturing the inner architecture of generational and gender relations at the domestic level, the PI may be superior for the identification of the channels that may have affected economic behavior and value formation at the individual level. Unlike Todd's – and most other schemes based on household structure and marriage – the PI allows for making distinctions between various family types once account has been taken of gender relations through an explicit consideration of male domination among its diagnostic criteria. To the extent that Todd's classification of family systems leaves certain doubts about its source of information and the historicity of the patterns posited, the approach proposed here is superior by providing explicit information about the sample size, the period of observation, and the share of urban-rural population in the pooled data which came to constitute each country sample (Table 2 above). Finally, the continuous rating scale implemented in the Index provides a more sensitive metric for the assessment of the intensity of familial behavior in a given population than fixed categories (like in Todd) or dichotomous measures (like in Dilli) (for detailed evidence based on the comparison of Carmichael's index and the PI, see Szołtysek and Poniat 2018).

RESULTS

Hypotheses and Stylized Facts

Our general hypothesis is that centuries-old patterns of familial patriarchy—either directly, through their survival over time, or indirectly, through their internalization in values, customs, and culture—are strongly associated with current regional disparities

¹³ A more qualitative assessment of the scattered data from Russia, customarily a troublesome case, also leads to safeguarding the reliability of our measures which were derived by pooling together data (altogether for 85 villages/settlements with 46,296 persons) from nearly 200 years of Russian history (1710-1897), and from such diverse contexts as the newly settled areas in the Urals, as well as established rural communities in the Central Black Earth Region; rural communities in sparsely populated rural regions with harsh ecological conditions; and those located in more environmentally friendly areas in the vicinity of urban centers.

across Europe in the areas we considered, i.e. in gender hierarchies, value orientations and developmental gradients. Before running more complex statistical models, we made some more specific predictions about the effects of historical family forms on the selected societal outcomes and proposed three *a priori* hypotheses.

Hypothesis 1. *Countries that had elevated PI levels in the past tend to preserve more rigid gender hierarchies in the present, whereas those with low scores on the PI scale are more likely to be associated with more egalitarian and gender-balanced outcomes*

[**Alternative:** *There is no, or a reverse correlation between past elevated PI levels and today's egalitarian and gender-balance characteristics*]

It has been increasingly recognized that while underdevelopment may enhance gender and other forms of inequality, societies hold certain cultural views, historically embedded, that may cast a long shadow on beliefs and values regarding the appropriate role of women (Duflo 2012; Jayachandran 2015; Alesina et al. 2013; Hansen et al. 2015; Olsson and Paik 2016; also Bisin and Verdier 2015). Deeply rooted patriarchal values from the last three hundred years are likely to persist, and hence become the long-lived sources of male and female identity. Because patriarchal family structures are characterized by customs and attitudes that collectively serve to maximize fertility (e.g., Dyson and Moore 1983), they create incentives for women to remain subordinate in exchange for receiving support in raising their children, thus decreasing the former's bargaining power (Galor and Klemp 2014). Patriarchal pre-adult socialization practices and parental concerns about exposing daughters to outside influences (female virginity) further inhibit women from exercising agency outside of the domestic sphere, thus limiting their access to education, employment, and training (Caldwell 1981; De Baca et al. 2014; Grogan 2007). Finally, in many patriarchal societies, family honor depends on the sexual purity of women, and girls tend to marry at very young ages (Gruber and Szołtysek 2016; Caldwell 1981, 10-11; Cain 1988).

Hypothesis 2. *Countries characterized historically by strong patriarchal traits tend to preserve a more collectivist mindset and exhibit a weaker social prevalence of emancipatory values in the present*

[**Alternative:** *There is no, or a reverse correlation between past elevated PI levels and today's prevalence of emancipatory values*]

Olsson and Paik (2016) provided links between hierarchical value systems emerging after the Neolithic Revolution and current beliefs. By the same token, specific patterns of family organization may lead to a development of lasting individual psychological and behavioral dispositions affecting societies through bottom-up aggregation. Family loyalty and interdependence characteristic of patriarchal societies are generally considered the defining components of the cross-cultural dimension of collectivism-individualism, with collectivism positively associated with strong family ties in multiple

cross-cultural studies (e.g., Vandello and Cohen 1999; Gelfand et al. 2004; Fincher and Thornhill 2012; also Alesina and Giuliano 2010; also Reher 1998, 203). Evidence from traditional family- and kinship-based agrarian economies has shown that the underlying patriarchal authority structures are often consciously safeguarded by child-rearing practices that oppose fostering or even allowing competitiveness and individual initiative in children during their upbringing (Caldwell 1981, 15). Because of its strong emphasis on loyalty to family, lineage, and kin, a patriarchal family structure restricts interactions between the family and the public sphere, and discourages family members from forming cooperative relationships with non-relatives. By this, it limits potentially stimulating “peer group effects” on development of more open value systems, instead rewarding conformity and normative behavior and reduced trust in strangers, which may be fairly immune to top-down policy interventions (Ermisch and Gambetta 2010; Alexander and Welzel 2015).

Hypothesis 3. *Historically more patriarchal countries will more likely yield weaker indicators of economic growth and general human development in the present*

[**Alternative:** *There is no, or a reverse correlation between past elevated PI levels and today's economic growth and general human development*]

In the male- and adult-centered patriarchal *milieu* the mobility of offspring is strongly limited (Caldwell 1982), human capital acquisition by younger and female family members is discouraged by familial pressures, and women tend to become “overspecialized” in reproductive, child-rearing, and domestic work. These hamper the acquisition of knowledge and skills through training or apprenticeship that would enable offspring (females in particular) to enter into labor and contractual relationships in the public sphere and to accumulate other forms of human capital and transmit it intergenerationally, thus stifling economic development in the longer run (Galor and Klemp 2014). Because patriarchal societies place a high premium on family loyalty and reverence for ancestors (i.e., a collectivist mindset), their members (especially females and the youngsters) are less prone to engage in the types of entrepreneurship, collaboration with non-kin, and risk-taking that are prerequisites for economic success (Whyte 1996). By rewarding conformity and normative behavior, and by reducing trust in strangers, patriarchal societies are also likely to be characterized by a high avoidance of uncertainty and generally a less individualist culture (Thornhill and Fincher 2014; also Ermisch and Gambetta 2010; Gorodnichenko and Roland 2011; Mokyr 2016; also Ang 2015). Because patriarchal structures hinder the ability of women to provide information, education, and cognitive skills to their offspring (Kambhampati and Rajan 2008; Grogan 2007), their effects tend to accumulate over time. In contrast, constraints on the power of the patriarch or the parents would improve incentives and property rights of women (and young men) and therefore the quality of decision making at that level (Dilli 2017), leading towards more egalitarian achievements in human development.

Bivariate correlations

We start by inspecting unconditional correlations between our variable of interest – the PI – and selected measures of contemporary outcomes, which we group into three major complexes related to gender equality, value orientation (ideational sphere), and human development and growth (Figure 3a-3f). The variables we have considered to capture the above dimensions have been widely used in economic, political and cross-cultural literature. Given that well-known weaknesses of a standard p -value approach may become attenuated in the context of a small sample size of our study (e.g., Wasserstein and Lazar 2016), we decided to use bootstrapping and 95% confidence intervals (CI). Each of the subsequent correlations is based on 1,000 simulations and their confidence intervals were obtained with the use of the bias-corrected and accelerated (BCa) method (Efron 1987).

First, we looked at bivariate correlations between the historical PI and two selected contemporary gender inequality measures – Gender Inequality Index (GII) and the “Family” component of the Social Institutions and Gender Index (SIGI) (Figures 3a-3b)¹⁴. In both cases we find strong positive and statistically significant relationships between historical patriarchy and gender patterns today. The good match is most perceptible with GII ($r = .64$; 95% CI |0.43,0.78|), implying that along with the increase in historical patriarchy levels the probability that a given present-day country will be characterized by more gender inequality also increases pretty much linearly. The relationship between the PI and the “Discriminatory Family Code” component of SIGI looks similar, though it is weakened by the presence of some outliers, such as Lithuania (with a moderate-to-strong patriarchy in the past but with its SIGI *Family* score at the level of Norway), and some other post-Soviet republics (like Ukraine and Belarus).¹⁵

¹⁴ Gender Inequality Index measures gender inequalities in: reproductive health (maternal mortality ratio and adolescent birth rates); empowerment (proportion of parliamentary seats occupied by females and the proportion of adult females and males aged 25+ years with at least some secondary education); and economic status (labour market participation of the female and the male populations aged 15+ years); see <http://hdr.undp.org/en/content/gender-inequality-index-gii>. Higher values indicate more gender inequality. The “Family” component of the Social Institutions and Gender Index measures a country’s “Discriminatory Family code” with regards to marriage, parental authority, and inheritance rights in 2014 (OECD Development Centre, Social Institutions and Gender Index 2014. Synthesis Report, 61–64; <https://www.genderindex.org/countries/?region=europe-and-central-asia>). We focus on this component because it yields global estimates for the largest number of countries from our collection, as well as for reasons of this component’s substantial affinity to our PI.

¹⁵ These patterns can be explained either by a recent strong commitment to gender equality and enacting laws protecting women’s rights, as in the case of Lithuania; or by *de jure* proclamation of gender equality which is, however, hardly implemented in legal practice, as in the post-Soviet republics just mentioned.

Figure 3A-3F. Unconditional cross-country correlations between historical patriarchy (PI) and selected measures of gender inequality, value orientations, economic growth and human development.

We followed similar procedures with regards to the two selected measures of value orientation and obtained even more suggestive results (Figures 3c-3d). In both cases a country's historical patriarchy profile is strongly and inversely related to the strength of emancipatory and individualistic values today. High patriarchy in the past strongly increases the probability that a country will have a low score on the Emancipatory Value Index (henceforth EVI), a recent reformulation of Inglehart's seminal measure of "survival versus self-expression values" (Welzel 2013).¹⁶

The relationship is fairly linear and has no particular outliers. With the Pearson r of -0.73 and plausible values of the true correlation as expressed by a 95% confidence interval ranging from -.55 to -0.83, the estimate is very satisfactory from the accuracy point of view. Accordingly, we found an inverse and equally strong association of the PI with one of Hofstede's "dimensions of culture" (*Individualism*)¹⁷. Also here, there is a fair amount of certainty in the true magnitude of the effect.

As indicated by the last set of scatterplots (Figures 3e-3f), the PI is also associated with the two most popular measures of development: contemporary *per capita* GDP (logged) and the Human Development Index (HDI). The observed negative correlations are in line with theoretical expectations (e.g., Bertrand and Schoar 2006); they both appear to be very general and downward sloping, and not driven by a small number of influential outliers. This purports to saying that for countries with strong patriarchal traits in the past there is a significant increase in the probability of being characterized by low economic output and lowered human development in the present. In the case of both variables the observed relationship is very strong, as even the lower boundaries of 95% confidence intervals (above -0.70 point estimate) would represent a genuinely large (negative) effect.

Multivariate analysis

A lurking threat to the interpretations above is the possibility that the PI may be correlated with unobserved country characteristics resulting in biased estimates of the effect of patriarchy on current developmental outcomes. In order to determine whether the associations predicted by historical family systems are not spuriously driven we examined them against a host of covariates. Our choice of controls was based on a respective hypothesis under investigation, whenever possible taking the same set of base-

¹⁶ It is the 12-item index introduced by Welzel (2013, 57–104) based on responses taken from the World Values Surveys (WVS), measuring the belief in freedom of choice and equality of opportunities over four domains, each of which summarizes three items: (1) equity values: an orientation that prioritizes gender equality over patriarchy; (2) liberty values: an orientation that prioritizes reproductive freedoms over their restriction; (3) autonomy values: an orientation that prioritizes self-determination over obedience; (4) expression values: an orientation that prioritizes voice over order.

¹⁷ It measures (at the national level) the strength of a preference for a loosely-knit social framework in which individuals are expected to take care only of themselves and their immediate families (its opposite being collectivism). See Hofstede et al., 2010; also <https://geert-hofstede.com>.

line control variables as used in previous research to ensure comparability. The chosen covariates were grouped into four major categories: *historical data characteristics* consider the average timing of the patriarchy score for each country; *historical development* controls include the backward GDP reconstructions corresponding to the time of patriarchy score¹⁸, the time elapsed since the first transition to agriculture (*Neolithic Revolution*; Putterman and Weil 2010), as well as the measure of the state antiquity (Bockstette et al. 2002)¹⁹; *bio-geographic endowments* include the climatic configuration of a country called the “Cool Water” (CW-) condition captured by an indexed measure proposed by Welzel (2013; henceforth: CWI), as well as the historical pathogens prevalence (Murray and Schaller 2010; Fincher and Thornhill 2012). Finally, we account for two great socio-cultural, political and institutional transformations by including dummies for the *Protestant* heritage of the country and its experience of *Communism*.

A natural framework in which to test our hypotheses is a regression where a selected contemporary trait is the dependent variable, as in the form:

$$y_c = \alpha + \beta P_{cT} + T_c + X_{c1-4} + u_c$$

where y_c denotes respective current developmental or value measure at the country level; P_c is this country's level of historical family patriarchy; T is the historical period that varies depending on the country; X_c represents a vector of a country's other controls (historical-developmental; biogeographic; social transformations), and u_c is the error term.

In each model the PI serves as the main explanatory variable. However, since the PI estimates are time-dependent²⁰, all of our specifications also control for the period of patriarchy “observation” in each country allowing it to differ accordingly²¹. If the measure of patriarchy is from a more distant time period, then it is plausible that we may observe a weaker relationship between the historical measure and contemporary developmental outcomes.

¹⁸ Historical GDP data are derived from the data file created by the Maddison Project. In the case of some countries (e.g. Belarus), with GDP data only from the 20th century we have used data describing their nearest neighbors or former rulers (like the Russian Empire, in this case). Data source: <https://www.rug.nl/ggdc/historicaldevelopment/maddison/releases/maddison-project-database-2018>.

¹⁹ The effects of some further potential confounders – such as the percent rural datasets in the sample and historical urbanization (the latter commonly used in the literature) – have been reduced already at the stage of computing the PI, and hence they were not considered in the model specification.

²⁰ For example, the Albanian patriarchy score refers to 1918, meaning that the time span between the reference period and the presence is „only” one hundred years; on the other hand, the Croatian PI levels are from 1674, hence nearly two and a half centuries earlier.

²¹ To some extent this also helps mitigate potentially confounding effects of the unobserved historical characteristics and/or processes (economic change, institutional and legal reforms, etc.).

In all subsequent models the selection of additional controls was decided depending on their theoretical relevance to the hypothesis under test. In each case, the presumption was that a given set of covariates could affect respective response variables through channels other than the one we are interested in identifying. Given the small *N*, the number of regressors in a single model was restricted to the most relevant ones and they were entered one at a time to avoid over-fitting. Crucially, in all regressions the bootstrap approximation was applied to the distribution of the least squares estimates and standard errors (involving 1,000 random samplings with replacement for each model; the bias-corrected and accelerated (BCa) method was used to obtain confidence intervals).²²

Table 3. Cross-country variation in gender inequality

	GII	GII	GII	GII	SIGI Family	SIGI Family	SIGI Family	SIGI Family
Historical PI	0.61*** -0.14	0.53*** -0.17	0.45* -0.19	0.13 -0.18	0.53*** -0.16	0.42** -0.15	0.46^ -0.26	0.25 -0.29
Time Period	0.16 -0.14	0.04 -0.27	0.12 -0.15	-0.03 -0.14	0.16 -0.2	0.04 -0.21	0.15 -0.2	0.05 -0.22
Neolithic Revolution		0.38^ -0.22				0.61** -0.22		
Protestantism			-0.25 -0.19				-0.09 -0.26	
Cool Water effect				-0.71** -0.24				-0.41 -0.32
Intercept	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	26	24	26	26	25	23	25	25
Adj. R-squared	0.39	0.4	0.4	0.61	0.29	0.56	0.27	0.34
F-statistic	9.03**	6.19**	6.61**	13.92***	5.99**	10.42**	4.05*	5.27**
AIC	65.7	61.57	66.06	55.1	67.06	52.22	68.51	65.88

Notes: cross-country OLS estimates, bootstrapped standard errors (based on 1,000 replications) in parentheses. In columns 1-4, the dependent variable is Gender Inequality Index from 2015; in columns 5-8 - the "Discriminatory Family Code" component of the Social Institutions and Gender Index (SIGI) as of 2014. ^ p-value <0.1 * p-value <0.05 ** p-value <0.01 *** p-value <0.001

Table 3 presents the results of OLS estimations for the relationship between the PI and gender inequality measures. It shows that historical family data are fairly good predictors of contemporary cross-country differences in inequalities between the sexes. In the model specification with PI and *Time period*, a one-standard deviation increase of the PI value is associated with an increase of GII by 0.61 standard deviation. This is a substantively important effect equal to a change by 95 index points, equivalent to a dif-

²² We have used procedures implemented in the library boot of R language.

ference in gender inequality levels between the Netherlands and Croatia. Controlling for the timing of the Neolithic Revolution or *Protestantism* (columns 2 and 3) – both of which enter the regression as expected²³ – does not eliminate the role of the PI as the most significant covariate in the models. Its increase by one-standard deviation still results in an increase by 0.53 and 0.45 standard deviation in GII, respectively – i.e., in magnitudes only a little smaller than those of the basic model. Each of these three models produces R-squared of about .40, thus accounting for a non-negligible part of the variation in contemporary gender inequalities. Historical patriarchy stops being statistically significant only after the CWI is included as a control variable (column 4), which is not surprising given that both variables are strongly correlated ($r=-0.708$, significant at the 0.01 level). It stands to reason to argue that patterns of household formation and marriage, by being an important component of our index, provide a plausible, if not major, transmission channel through which biogeographic endowments have impacted contemporary gender relations (cf. Santos Silva et al. 2017).

The PI also appears to be a passable predictor of contemporary gender inequalities with regards to legal standing in marriage, parental authority, and inheritance rights as captured by Sigi's Discriminatory Family Code variable, whereby higher levels of historical patriarchy are associated with a more deterred position of women in the present, holding all else constant. Both in the basic specification with *Time period* (column 5) as well as in the model conditioning on the timing of the Neolithic Revolution (column 6), the effect of the PI is substantial and fairly stable. The latter model also suggests (in line with Hansen et al. 2015) that societies with longer histories of agriculture may have less equality in gender roles in the present, and that this may happen in part independently from their historical patriarchy levels. By accounting for the effect of *Protestantism* in column (7) we obtain results whereby historically high patriarchy levels still appear to be positively associated with contemporary gender inequality, but the precision of this model becomes more uncertain. Meanwhile, controlling for CWI (column 8) does not yield any significant associations.

In turn, the inspection of Table 4 shows a strong and statistically significant association between the PI and emancipatory values (EVI) in nearly all five model specifications. In each model, higher patriarchy levels correspond to a weaker prevalence of emancipatory values in a country holding all else constant. To obtain an impression of the economic significance, we note that the result of our basic model (with *Time period* only) implies that a one-standard deviation increase in the PI is associated with a decrease in the prevalence of emancipatory values by nearly 0.20 index points in EVI, amounting to a shift in the individualism scale from the levels of Austria to those of Albania. The importance of the PI decreases somewhat after the effects of *Protestantism* are controlled for (column 3), with Protestant countries scoring higher on the emancipatory value scale, as expected. Even in this case, however, one standard deviation increase in the PI leads to a decrease in EVI by approximately 0.11 points. Though this is

²³ For evidence that a Protestant religious heritage improves the status of women in a country, see Inglehart and Norris 2003.

still a statistically significant result, it may contain both substantively meaningful as well as negligible effects ([0.64, -0.03]). Contrary to expectations, neither the CWI nor historical pathogen loads enter the emancipatory values regression with significant coefficients (columns 4 and 5), while patriarchy holds still. This is consistent with the view that the PI could act as a transmission channel for those variables. In the last model for EVI (column 5), the effect size of patriarchy becomes particularly strong: the estimated coefficient suggests an economically large relationship with the spread of emancipatory values that is about six times the effect of historical pathogen prevalence.

Similar results are achieved when one of Hofstede's "dimensions of culture" (Hofstede et al., 2010) is chosen as our response variable (columns 6-10 in Table 4). Also here, historically higher patriarchy levels are invariably associated with lower contemporary individualism scores, but the models' statistical and substantive significance and their explanatory power are greater compared to regressions with EVI. For example, in four out of five specifications, an increase in PI by one-standard deviation leads to a decrease in individualism by over 0.8 standard deviation, i.e., by 20 index points – roughly the difference between Poland and the Netherlands. Moreover, the effect of historical patriarchy is fairly robust to the inclusion of other covariates, of which only the CWI enters the model with a significantly positive and strong coefficient (as expected; see Welzel 2013).

As shown in Table 5, historical PI also tends to be significantly and negatively associated with contemporary (2016) GDP *per capita* in all seven model specifications. In all models, standardized coefficients of PI are generally above 0.6, and in two cases close to 0.8, indicating an economically important effect of historical family systems. For example, in column (1), the PI's increase by a one-standard deviation results in a difference in real GDP values by nearly 100% (equivalent to the difference between Slovakia and Spain). The relationship between patriarchy and economic output would tend to be economically substantial even if the true correlation fell near the lower boundaries of the 95% confidence intervals (point estimate of -0.70). Noteworthy, the PI turns out to be a better predictor of contemporary cross-country differences in economic performance than Maddison's estimates of historical GDP (column 2), or the time elapsed since the Neolithic Revolution (column 3), and is also robust to controlling for the effects of *CWI*, *Protestantism*, or *State Antiquity* (columns 4, 5, and 7, respectively). The effects of the PI are also not wiped out after accounting for cross-country differences in the experience of Communism (column 6), which exert strong and independent impact on contemporary GDP levels.²⁴ A one-standard deviation increase in PI in this model is still associated with a decrease of predicted real GDP by 0.43 standard deviation, thus implying a shift in a country's economic output by roughly 40 percent.

²⁴ Partial r-squared for PI in this model equals to 0.26, and for Communism to 0.34.

Table 4. Cross-country variation in value orientations

	EVI	EVI	EVI	EVI	EVI	Ind.	Ind.	Ind.	Ind.	Ind.
Historical PI	-0.73*** -0.12	-0.79*** -0.17	-0.38** -0.16	-0.46* -0.23	-0.88*** -0.14	-0.87*** -0.1	-0.88*** -0.13	-0.83*** -0.14	-0.53*** -0.14	-0.88*** -0.14
Time Period	0.16 -0.16	0.31 -0.3	0.25 -0.13	0.2 -0.16	0.14 -0.23	0.1 -0.11	0.22 -0.16	0.11 -0.1	0.24* -0.11	0.14 -0.23
Neolithic Revolution		-0.14 -0.26					-0.23 -0.22			
Protestantism			0.59** -0.19					0.08 -0.14		
Cool Water effect				0.39 -0.28					0.53** -0.17	
Pathogen load					0.14 -0.33					0.14 -0.34
Intercept	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	24	22	24	24	22	25	23	25	25	23
Adj. R-squared	0.51	0.48	0.62	0.52	0.5	0.67	0.78	0.67	0.8	0.64
F-statistic	12.87***	7.49**	13.45***	9.61***	8.15**	24.88***	27.02***	19.92***	32.56***	14.22***
AIC	55.88	55.27	50.57	55.66	54.01	48.37	37.99	49.21	36.62	43.79

Notes: cross-country OLS estimates, bootstrapped standard errors (based on 1,000 replications) in parentheses. In columns 1-5, the dependent variable is Emancipatory Value Index (time-pooled cross section country aggregates from WVS Waves 1 to 6); in columns 6-10 – one of Hofstede's "dimensions of culture" (*Individualism*), measuring the degree of interdependence a society maintains among its members (time-pooled cross section country aggregates from Hofstede et al., 2010; also <https://geert-hofstede.com>).

^ p-value <0.1 * p-value <0.05 ** p-value <0.01 *** p-value <0.001

Table 5. Cross-country variation in economic performance

	GDP (ln)	GDP (ln)	GDP (ln)				
Historical PI	-0.83*** (0.10)	-0.68*** (0.19)	-0.79*** (0.11)	-0.60*** (0.12)	-0.69*** (0.13)	-0.43** (0.13)	-0.65*** (0.13)
Time period	0.01 (0.09)	-0.15 (0.18)	0.09 (0.22)	0.08 (0.10)	0.02 (0.10)	-0.10 (0.08)	-0.08 (0.11)
Hist. GDP (ln)		0.23 (0.30)					
Neolithic Revolution			-0.10 (0.12)				
Cool Water effect				0.38^ (0.18)			
Protestantism					0.22 (0.15)		
Communism						-0.51** (0.16)	
State Antiquity							0.31^ (0.15)
Intercept	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	26	25	24	26	26	26	26
Adj. R-squared	0.68	0.68	0.64	0.72	0.70	0.78	0.73
F-statistic	27.76***	18.29***	14.88***	22.91***	20.26***	30.92***	24.28***
AIC	48.84	48.50	48.60	45.29	48.31	39.82	44.14

Notes: cross-country OLS estimates, bootstrapped standard errors (based on 1,000 replications) in parentheses. In all columns, the dependent variable is per capita gross domestic product of 2016 (transformed by taking the natural logarithm; source: the World Bank).

^ p-value <0.1 * p-value <0.05 ** p-value <0.01 *** p-value <0.001

Similar results are obtained when the same covariates, including the PI, are regressed on the values of HDI from 2015 (Table 6). Given that the GDP index in the HDI is based on GDP *per capita*, this can hardly be surprising. Interestingly, however, the HDI's greater accountability of non-economic elements of development results in revealing a stronger and more robust relationship with PI. Same as in the models with GDP, the effect of historical patriarchy is invariably negative and statistically significant, even after controlling for selected covariates. Of the latter, *CWI*, *Protestantism* and the experience of Communism enter regressions with significant coefficients and expected direction, but only the former surpasses the effect size of the PI. In this worst scenario, where the standardized Beta coefficient for the PI falls below 0.5, a one standard deviation increase in historical patriarchy still represents an economically substantial change in the value of HDI (by 62 index points).

Table 6. Cross-country variation in human development

	HDI	HDI	HDI	HDI	HDI	HDI	HDI
Historical PI	-0.82*** (0.10)	-0.71*** (0.17)	-0.77*** (0.12)	-0.45*** (0.09)	-0.65*** (0.12)	-0.50** (0.18)	-0.71*** (0.14)
Time period	-0.07 (0.10)	-0.11 (0.16)	0.05 (0.22)	0.08 (0.09)	-0.03 (0.10)	-0.14 [^] (0.08)	-0.11 (0.10)
Hist. GDP (ln)		0.14 (0.25)					
Neolithic Revolution			-0.23 (0.17)				
Cool Water effect				0.56*** (0.14)			
Protestantism					0.26 [^] (0.15)		
Communism						-0.39 [^] (0.21)	
State Antiqui- ty							0.18 (0.17)
Intercept	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	26	25	24	26	26	26	26
Adj. R- squared	0.67	0.70	0.66	0.80	0.70	0.72	0.68
F-statistic	26.38***	19.66***	15.87***	35.03***	20.26***	22.79***	18.59***
AIC	49.77	45.26	48.32	37.16	48.31	46.03	49.93

Notes: cross-country OLS estimates, bootstrapped standard errors (based on 1,000 replications) in parentheses. In all columns, the dependent variable is Human Development Index of 2015 (source: United Nations Development Program (2016). *Human development report 2016*. New York, 198-201).

[^] p-value <0.1 * p-value <0.05 ** p-value <0.01 *** p-value <0.001

Robustness checks

Because the number of observations that are used for the above-presented regressions is relatively small, we used the procedure for identifying the influence of particular observations on our model estimates. We then re-estimated all model specifications on subpopulations of Mosaic/NAPP countries omitting some potentially problematic observations. The identification of potentially "problematic" cases was carried out in two different ways. First, we have excluded four countries for which Mosaic data were the least representative (Bulgaria, Croatia, Spain and Turkey), on the grounds that their PI estimates may be biased and hence create spurious correlations in the models. Our exclusion criteria were concerned either with a country's meagre representation in our database (e.g., only one very early population corresponding to modern day Croatia; exclusive focus on Istanbul as regards Turkey); or on the presumption that a country's collection of data was too regionally clustered (two Bulgarian populations based on numerous small censuses from different periods; Spain represented by two populations only

from Catalonia). All the models we have presented above were then re-run on the basis of such a curtailed sample.

Additionally, we have run residuals and leverage tests based on the Cook's distances derived from the full (based on the full countries sample) models. Highly influential cases observed separately for each model were then removed from the sample one at a time, each time refitting the regression model on the remaining countries. Since Cook's D doesn't have a one-standard and common accepted cut-off point, we have decided to use the formula $D_i > 4/n$ and discard values above 0.15. The new models were rerun only for the instances when at least one observation was above that point, and in due course we found that the number of discarded observations was never greater than 3.

The results of these tests showed that even after removing particular observations our results remained stable, both in terms of estimation and inference. The new models obtained by curtailing the dataset were very similar to those based on the full country sample (see Appendix: Section I, Tables 1A-1F). The PI effects, their direction and sizes are in almost every case identical with those from the full models. Important differences were identified only in the models with *SIGI_Family* as the dependent variable, and *PI*, *Time period* and *Protestantism* as the predictors (columns 5 and 6, Table 1B in Appendix: Section I), which turned out to be decidedly weak. Given that even the whole model based on the 25 countries instead of 21 and 23 was relatively weak and PI influence was significant only at the 90% level, this finding does not seem to undermine our core findings.

DISCUSSION

In general, our results appear to confirm that historical family patterns in Europe have a significant and strong association with current regional disparities in gender inequality, value orientations, and economic and human development. Four main causal paths could account for these associations. First, family structures may persist to the present and continue to affect contemporary outcomes directly. This form of persistence seems intuitively likely given that family behavior and values represent "deep" cultural layers which are transmitted from generation to generation and move slowly over time (Reher 1998; Therborn 2004; also Bisin and Verdier 2000). Studies in family history have substantiated this observation by revealing a strong continuity of demographic behavior, at least in some areas of Europe (Reher 1997; Wall 2001; Mironov 2016; also Dalla Zuanna and Micheli 2004).

Second, the persistence may develop through intermediate factors, such as the nature of political or economic institutions that have been shaped first by family structures and have continued to influence contemporary societies in a path-dependent manner. For example, in the 1980s, after Peter Laslett showed that the nuclear family structure had been the dominant family type in England long before the Industrial Revolution, some scholars (including Laslett himself) argued that the dominance of the nuclear

family was among the necessary preconditions for modernization and industrialization, which could then spill over further developmental outcomes irrespective of subsequent family change.

Third, reverse causation is also plausible in that the differences in economic and institutional factors across countries might have themselves caused the variation in family structures. Greif (2006), for example, pointed out a potential feedback mechanism where on the one hand, nuclear families facilitate the development of corporate institutions, but on the other the socioeconomic transformations related to that development encourage the formation of nuclear families across Europe (also Dennison and Ogilvie 2014, 672-685).

Finally, another possibility is that the links between family structures and developmental gradients are an outcome of a deeper underlying determinant. In this case, family structures would be endogenous to the causal process and of little explanatory value.

There is nothing about our own results that makes causality automatic from past to present outcomes, and our analyses are not legitimate to rule out entirely the possibility of bidirectional or circular causation, or to assert that the links between family structures and developmental gradients are not an outcome of a deeper underlying determinant²⁵. However, the irreversibility of the temporal order of the relationships between historical family and our developmental measures can be elucidated by shifting the focus of the analysis to the first two types of causation just described, i.e. by examining the extent to which contemporary familial behaviors are related to historical family structures.

For the purpose of this exercise we focus on contemporary accounts of actual (experienced or current) practices related to family life and cohesion²⁶.

²⁵ Note, however, that our identification strategy allowed us to capture potential influences on our response variables other than those of historical patriarchy, including religion and historical development. In addition, we offered a number of theoretically informed guesses for why familial institutions might have played an exogenous role by suggesting that patriarchal structures from the last three hundred years may be prone to strong persistence (and even tend to accumulate over time), and hence remain fairly immune to top-down policy interventions (Alexander and Welzel 2015). A major challenge in this regard would be to identify an appropriate instrumentation strategy based on the introduction of an external source of variation in our focal explanatory variable which could be argued to be exogenous with respect to the chosen dependent variable. Typically, however, the two-stage least squares estimations used for that purpose are precluded in small-N studies like ours (Esping-Andersen 2007).

²⁶ We have chosen to focus on practices rather than on subjective measures of the strength of family ties (such as those of Alesina and Giuliano 2010 or Thornhill and Fincher 2014, 131) because values scores tend to be noticeably different from the practices scores across many recent cross-cultural studies (e.g., the GLOBE project; see House et al. 2004). For example, using data for 15 Mosaic/NAPP countries covered by the GLOBE project we established that *Gender Egalitarianism* and *In-group Collectivism* tended to be valued more than they were practiced (at the organizational level). Furthermore, for both variables, a clear linear positive relationship between Societal Values and Societal Practices could not be established. For *Gender Egalitarianism Societal Value* vs. *Gender Egali-*

Our first measure of contemporary family was Welzel's measure of "contemporary patriarchy" based on a series of responses World Values Surveys which combined scores for percent females who declared being married before the age 20, and for the percent married men (aged 30-34 years) who declared living with parents. In addition, we used the percent 30-39 years old living with parents, based on data from *European Values Study 2008*. We assume that earlier marriage may enhance more patriarchal conjugal relations (Gruber and Szołtysek 2016; Therborn 2004), and that the family ties might be considered stronger and more aligned with a complex hierarchy of authority patterns based on age, if the individual lives with his or her parents (Reher 1998; earlier Banfield 1958; also Todd 1985).

As a preliminary test of the degree of covariation between those measures, unconditional correlations between historical and contemporary data were plotted in Figures 4A-B (again, bootstrapping methods and 95% confidence intervals were used). The two correlations suggest that our data contain a strong signal. For both the *Contemporary Patriarchy* and the EVS data the relationship is fairly linear and has no particular outliers. In both cases, countries with higher patriarchal values in the past display higher frequencies of intergenerational co-residence in the present (and earlier marriage for women). The Pearson r of 0.80 or above, and plausible values of the true correlation as expressed by a 95% confidence interval ranging from 0.61 to 0.89 for the former variable, and from 0.74 and 0.94 for the latter one, imply very substantial effects.

Figures 4A-4B. The unconditional correlations between contemporary family ties, patriarchy and intergenerational coresidence, and historical patriarchy levels (PI)

arianism Societal Practices: $r = -0.1925403$, $t = -0.70745$, $df = 13$, $p\text{-value} = 0.4918$ (the same pattern for 22 European countries covered by the GLOBE); for *Collectivism II Societal Values (In-group Collectivism) vs. Collectivism II Societal Practices (In-group Collectivism)*: $r = 0.4450386$, $t = 1.7918$, $df = 13$, $p\text{-value} = 0.09645$. Own calculations based on http://globeproject.com/study_2004_2007#data.

Notes: EVS (2016): *European Values Study 2008: Integrated Dataset (EVS 2008)*. GESIS Data Archive, Cologne. ZA4800 Data file Version 4.0.0, [doi:10.4232/1.12458](https://doi.org/10.4232/1.12458).

The associations from Figures 4A-B were found to be robust to controlling for a host of potentially confounding factors in the multivariate framework (Tables 6-7). Out of sixteen regression specifications for the two response variables of interest, the PI turns out to be significantly associated in fifteen models, suggesting that countries with heightened historical patriarchy quite invariably tend to display stronger intergenerational bonding, and hence stronger family ties, today. Furthermore, in most specifications the size effects of the PI are large or even very large. The only exception is the model for *Contemporary Patriarchy* indicating that the negative and significant relationship between past and present family patterns is not robust to including the current log GDP estimates (column 7 in Table 6). Potential concerns over this issue are, however, partly allayed by the fact that similar qualification does not apply to regression with our second measure of contemporary behavior (see below). The association between historical and current patriarchy manifests itself most strongly in the model controlling for time period and historical pathogens (*ibid.*, column 2), in which an increase by one-standard deviation in PI corresponds to increase in the *Contemporary Patriarchy* scores by 0.90 standard deviation, roughly equal to the difference between Switzerland and Albania. The PI's impact on current family practices remains genuinely robust to the inclusion of *Protes-*

tantism (again, negatively correlated with the outcome variable), CWI, and the experience of Communism²⁷.

The regressions with the EVS data as dependent variable provide further consistent evidence which shows that higher patriarchy is related to contemporary tighter intergenerational bonds (Table 7). The results remain significant and strong across all specifications, even after controlling for the effect of Communism and the “cool-water” effect (both significant). Most noteworthy, the result is also robust to the inclusion of the contemporary log GDP, despite its otherwise strong effect on the outcome variable (an increase by one-standard deviation in GDP results in the decrease in the rates of contemporary co-residence by 0.56 standard deviation, equal to 5.3 index points). Same as in Table 6 above, historical pathogens, the experience of Protestantism, membership in the Soviet Union, and the variation in historical GDP do not matter, while the PI holds prominently in these models. For example, the results from column 2 purport to saying that a 4.6 point difference on the patriarchy scale could make a difference of about 9 percent points in contemporary co-residence, like, for example, between Austria (10.6%) and Lithuania (19.2%)²⁸.

²⁷ Interestingly, earlier membership in the Soviet Union does not enter the regression with significant sign, which might suggest that the specific Soviet-type of Communism had more impact on normative systems rather than on the actual behavior.

²⁸ Leverage tests revealed that these results are not subject to significant change with the removal of outlying cases (data available on request). Similar exercises performed for response variables measuring the normative aspect of family ties (Alesina/Giuliano’s and Thornhill/Fincher’s measures of the strength of family ties) established that the relationship between the PI and both indexes is positive and linear, although it tends to be wiped out by controlling for other covariates. The important exceptions were models indicating a strong positive linear relationship of historical patriarchy with contemporary family ties controlling for a country’s experience of belonging to the USSR (of an equally strong but adverse effect). In this case, the PI’s increase by one-standard deviation led to increase in the strength of family ties by over 0.62 standard deviation.

Table 7. Cross-country variation in contemporary patriarchy

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Historical PI	0.83***	0.90***	0.57***	0.30*	0.78***	0.50**	0.18	0.74**
	-0.13	-0.17	-0.16	-0.14	-0.17	-0.19	-0.18	-0.23
Time Period	-0.03	0	-0.08	0.06	-0.01	-0.16	0.02	0.05
	-0.13	-0.14	-0.14	-0.09	-0.15	-0.13	-0.08	-0.25
Pathogen load		-0.13						
		-0.28						
Protestantism			-0.46**					
			-0.16					
Communism				0.68***				
				-0.15				
Post-soviet					0.13			
					-0.17			
Cool Water effect						-0.59*		
						-0.24		
GDP In							-0.75***	
							-0.19	
Historical GDP In								-0.1
								-0.42
Intercept	Yes							
N	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	20
Adj.R-squared	0.61	0.59	0.63	0.65	0.6	0.75	0.72	0.65
F-statistic	16.51***	10.77***	12.38***	13.52***	10.99***	20.74***	18.22***	12.66***
AIC	44.69	46.21	44.25	42.96	45.92	36.25	38.35	40.35

Notes: cross-country OLS estimates, bootstrapped standard errors (based on 1,000 replications) in parentheses. The dependent variable is Welzel's measure of contemporary patriarchy (time-pooled cross section country aggregates from WVS Waves 1-6; data: courtesy of C. Welzel).

^ p-value <0.1 * p-value <0.05 ** p-value <0.01 *** p-value <0.001

Table 8. Cross-country variation in contemporary residential proximity

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Historical PI	0.98***	0.95***	0.74***	0.49*	1.08***	0.67***	0.50**	0.90***
	-0.1	-0.15	-0.21	-0.2	-0.14	-0.16	-0.19	-0.2
Time Period	0.05	0.01	0	0.1	0.03	-0.03	0.06	0.14
	-0.1	-0.11	-0.13	-0.09	-0.11	-0.11	-0.1	-0.2
Pathogen load		0.1						
		-0.25						
Protestantism			-0.3					
			-0.19					
Communism				0.56**				
				-0.2				
Post-soviet					-0.15			
					-0.15			
Cool Water effect						-0.42*		
						-0.21		
GDP ln							-0.56*	
							-0.23	
Historical GDP ln								-0.13
								-0.27
Intercept	Yes							
N	23	22	23	23	23	23	23	22
Adj. R-squared	0.76	0.74	0.78	0.83	0.76	0.79	0.85	0.75
F-statistic	36.46***	21.27***	26.80***	36.13***	24.37***	28.35***	41.55***	22.58***
AIC	36.92	37.78	36.19	30.48	37.94	35.13	27.72	37.78

Notes: cross-country OLS estimates, bootstrapped standard errors (based on 1,000 replications) in parentheses. The dependent variable is percent 30-39 years old living with parents, based on EVS (2016): European Values Study 2008: Integrated Dataset (EVS 2008). GESIS Data Archive, Cologne. ZA4800 Data file Version 4.0.0, doi:10.4232/1.12458).

^ p-value <0.1 * p-value <0.05 ** p-value <0.01 *** p-value <0.001

CONCLUSIONS

This study is the first to put the analysis of the relationship between historical family organization and contemporary developmental outcomes into a unified empirical framework based on a massive repository of newly available historical data. Its major finding is that historical family organization is associated with developmental and value disparities among European nations today. We have showed that countries which once had elevated patriarchy levels in the past generally tended to preserve more hierarchical gender structures, more collectivist mindsets, and weaker indicators of economic and human development today. In most cases these relations emerge even when statistically controlling for other variables that are correlated with historical patriarchy and that might also be expected to independently predict particular cross-country differences. In an effort toward understanding what drives these correlations, we have made informed suggestions that family patterns are very persistent. Accordingly, we have tested these presumptions empirically showing that familial behavior today and family patterns in the past are, indeed, strongly and robustly correlated and that this persistence is not likely to be a sole by-product of differences in current economic development. This may suggest that the principles of family organization at the grassroots of society could be one of the intermediate variables accounting for contemporary cultural and developmental divergence within Europe.

Further research should strive to test if the main insight of this paper remains intact by employing our measure of historical family to a wider assembly of settings (be those countries or their subdivisions) and taking into account other correlates (including spatial autocorrelation) and the potential for reverse causation. Should the results of those future endeavors indeed prove to suggest that historical family patterns cast a very long shadow on recent developmental outcomes, then certain recommendations can be made for policy-makers to show greater sensitivity to historical path dependencies in the familial and demographic realm, and to bear in mind the specific characteristics of family systems when designing social policies.

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The Power of the Family:

New Data Reveal the Role of the Historical Family as the Instigator of Disparate and Lasting Developmental Trajectories

Supplementary Material: Online Appendix

This document is the Online Appendix to our journal article “The Power of the Family”. It comprises three sections. Section I provides additional tables with robustness tests to our data on cross-country variation in gender inequality, value orientation, economic output and human development. Section II provides details to the Mosaic and NAPP data files. Section III provides all references to the data. Feedback to our analyses is highly welcome; if you wish to provide your feedback, please write to mszoltis@gmail.com.

Online Appendix: Section I*Table 1A.* Cross-country variation in gender inequality (robustness tests with selected countries omitted)

	GII – 1	GII –2a	GII –2b	GII –3	GII – 4a	GII – 4b
Historical PI	0.67***	0.63**	0.63**	0.51*	0.16	0.17
	-0.16	-0.21	-0.2	-0.21	-0.27	-0.16
Time Period	0.11	-0.07	-0.18	0.05	0.03	-0.11
	-0.15	-0.31	-0.31	-0.15	-0.16	-0.14
Neolithic Revolution		0.33	0.31			
		-0.27	-0.27			
Protestantism				-0.27		
				-0.19		
Cool Water effect					-0.65*	-0.75***
					-0.3	-0.22
Intercept	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	22	20	22	22	22	25
Adj. R-squared	0.44	0.41	0.38	0.46	0.58	0.66
F-statistic	9.28**	5.50**	5.28**	6.90**	10.56***	16.76***
AIC	54.41	52.05	57.93	54.57	49.07	49.37
Omitted countries	Bulgaria,	Bulgaria,	Croatia,	Bulgaria,	Bulgaria,	Great Britain
	Croatia,	Croatia,	Turkey	Croatia,	Croatia,	
	Spain,	Spain,		Spain,	Spain,	
	Turkey	Turkey		Turkey	Turkey	

Notes: cross-country OLS estimates, bootstrapped standard errors (based on 1,000 replications) in parentheses. The dependent variable is Gender Inequality Index from 2015. Model specifications in columns (3) and (6) based on Cook's distances.

^ p-value <0.1 * p-value <0.05 ** p-value <0.01 *** p-value <0.001

Table 1B. Cross-country variation in gender inequality (robustness tests with selected countries omitted)

	SIGI – 1a	SIGI – 1b	SIGI – 2a	SIGI – 2b	SIGI – 3a	SIGI – 3b	SIGI – 4a	SIGI – 4b
Historical	0.47*	0.45**	0.42*	0.32*	0.47	0.23	0.28	0.04
PI	-0.21	-0.16	-0.21	-0.15	-0.38	-0.34	-0.42	-0.39
Time	0.18	0.30^	0.19	0.16	0.18	0.25	0.15	0.13
Period	-0.2	-0.17	-0.33	-0.28	-0.23	-0.22	-0.24	-0.22
Neolithic Revolution			0.48^	0.56*				
			-0.27	-0.27				
Protestantism					0.01	-0.13		
					-0.35	-0.36		
Cool Water effect							-0.23	-0.44
							-0.4	-0.4
Intercept	Yes							
N	21	24	19	21	21	23	21	22
Adj. R- squared	0.22	0.34	0.38	0.46	0.18	0.18	0.21	0.19
F-statistic	3.96*	7.09**	4.67*	6.84**	2.52	2.58	2.79	2.66
AIC	58.92	62.71	51.24	52,51	60.84	66.37	60.17	63.34
Omitted countries	Bulgaria	Croatia	Bulgaria	Albania	Bulgaria	Albania	Bulgaria	Albania
	Croatia		Croatia	Croatia	Croatia	Croatia	Croatia	
	Spain		Spain		Spain		Spain	Turkey
	Turkey		Turkey		Turkey		Turkey	

Notes: cross-country OLS estimates, bootstrapped standard errors (based on 1,000 replications) in parentheses. The dependent variable is the “Discriminatory Family Code” component of the Social Institutions and Gender Index (SIGI) as of 2014. Model specifications in columns (2), (4), (6), and (8) based on Cook’s distances.

^ p-value <0.1 * p-value <0.05 ** p-value <0.01 *** p-value <0.001

Table 1C. Cross-country variation in value orientation (robustness tests with selected countries omitted)

	EVI – 1a	EVI – 1b	EVI – 2a	EVI – 2b	EVI – 3a	EVI – 3b	EVI – 4	EVI – 5a	EVI – 5b
Historical PI	-0.77***	-0.70***	-0.77***	-0.86***	-0.49**	-0.51***	-0.48*	-0.79***	-0.81***
	-0.14	-0.11	-0.17	-0.2	-0.17	-0.14	-0.23	-0.16	-0.16
Time Period	0.06	0.09	0.17	0.42	0.17	0.41***	0.1	0.15	0.01
	-0.15	-0.16	-0.25	-0.4	-0.11	-0.11	-0.15	-0.2	-0.3
Neolithic Revolution			-0.11	-0.2					
			-0.23	-0.4					
Protestantism					0.47*	0.53***			
					-0.21	-0.14			
Cool Water effect							0.36		
							-0.23		
Pathogen load								-0.11	0.11
								-0.32	-0.41
Intercept	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	22	23	20	20	22	21	22	20	20
Adj. R-squared	0.53	0.46	0.49	0.41	0.64	0.81	0.55	0.54	0.47
F-statistic	12.72***	12.53***	7.15**	5.48**	13.72***	28.81***	9.70***	8.62**	6.60**
AIC	52.72	55.71	50.45	52.99	45.23	30.65	50.25	48.02	50.94
Omitted countries	Bulgaria	Sweden	Bulgaria	Great Britain	Bulgaria	Great Britain	Bulgaria	Bulgaria	Spain
	Croatia		Croatia	Sweden	Croatia	Latvia	Croatia	Croatia	Sweden
	Spain		Spain		Spain	Norway	Spain	Spain	
	Turkey		Turkey		Turkey		Turkey	Turkey	

Notes: cross-country OLS estimates, bootstrapped standard errors (based on 1,000 replications) in parentheses. The dependent variable is Emancipatory Value Index (time-pooled cross section country aggregates from WVS Waves 1-6). Model specifications in columns (2), (4), (6), and (9) based on Cook’s distances.

^ p-value <0.1 * p-value <0.05 ** p-value <0.01 *** p-value <0.001

Table 1D. Cross-country variation in value orientation (robustness tests with selected countries omitted)

	Ind – 1	Ind – 2a	Ind –2b	Ind – 3	Ind – 4a	Ind – 4b	Ind – 5a	Ind –5b
Historical PI	-0.88***	-0.90***	-0.91***	-0.84***	-0.38*	-0.43**	-0.81***	-0.74***
	-0.13	-0.19	-0.11	-0.19	-0.18	-0.15	-0.16	-0.18
Time Period	0.1	0.3	0.24	0.11	0.16	0.25	0.01	0.25
	-0.14	-0.29	-0.2	-0.14	-0.13	-0.11	-0.31	-0.18
Neolithic Revolution		-0.21	-0.36*					
		-0.22	-0.16					
Protestantism				0.06				
				-0.17				
Cool Water effect					0.63***	0.60***		
					-0.17	-0.16		
Pathogen load							0.11	-0.22
							-0.41	-0.26
Intercept	Yes							
N	21	19	21	21	21	24	19	22
Adj. R-squared	0.62	0.73	0.88	0.62	0.79	0.81	0.56	0.69
F-statistic	17.66***	17.25***	51.96	11.74***	25.55***	33.16***	8.56*	16.48***
AIC	43.76	36.48	21.77	44.99	32.73	34.19	40.33	39.2
Omitted countries	Bulgaria	Bulgaria	Hungary	Bulgaria	Bulgaria	Turkey	Bulgaria	Austria
	Croatia	Croatia	Sweden	Croatia	Croatia		Croatia	
	Spain	Spain		Spain	Spain		Spain	
	Turkey	Turkey		Turkey	Turkey		Turkey	

Notes: cross-country OLS estimates, bootstrapped standard errors (based on 1,000 replications) in parentheses. The dependent variable is of Hofstede’s “Individualism” (time-pooled cross section country aggregates from Hofstede et al., 2010; also <https://geert-hofstede.com>). Model specifications in columns (3), (6), and (8) based on Cook’s distances.

^ p-value <0.1 * p-value <0.05 ** p-value <0.01 *** p-value <0.001

Table 1E. Cross-country variation in economic output (robustness tests with selected countries omitted)

	GDP-1a	GDP-1b	GDP-2a	GDP-2b	GDP-3a	GDP-3b	GDP-4a	GDP-4b	GDP-5a	GDP-5b	GDP-6a	GDP-6b	GDP-7a	GDP-7b
Historical PI	-0.84*** -0.11	-0.87*** -0.08	-0.70** -0.22	-0.69*** -0.2	-0.82*** -0.15	-0.83*** -0.15	-0.50** -0.17	-0.62*** -0.11	-0.69*** -0.15	-0.73*** -0.13	-0.34* -0.15	-0.38** -0.13	-0.63*** -0.18	-0.64*** -0.15
Time Period	-0.02 -0.12	-0.04 -0.1	-0.13 -0.19	-0.19 -0.2	0.18 -0.17	0.25 -0.25	0.03 -0.12	0.11 -0.1	0.03 -0.12	-0.01 -0.09	-0.05 -0.07	-0.1 -0.07	-0.05 -0.11	-0.16 -0.11
Historical GDP (ln)			0.19 -0.29	0.28 -0.25										
Neolithic Revolution					-0.16 -0.16	-0.18 -0.16								
CWI							0.44* -0.21	0.36** -0.14						
Protestant.									0.25 -0.16	0.21 -0.15				
Communism											-0.59*** -0.16	-0.61*** -0.13		
State Antiquity													0.32^ -0.19	0.31^ -0.16
Intercept	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	22	25	22	23	20	23	22	23	22	25	22	24	22	24
Adj. R-squared	0.7	0.74	0.68	0.77	0.66	0.65	0.75	0.79	0.71	0.76	0.81	0.89	0.74	0.78
F-statistic	24.28***	35.85***	15.95***	26.32***	13.11***	14.70***	21.99***	28.94***	18.31***	26.24***	30.23***	63.05***	20.74***	28.55***
AIC	41.5	41.7	42.87	37.08	41.1	46.47	37.52	34.75	40.63	40.98	31.85	20.75	38.53	37.14
Omitted countries	Bulgaria Croatia Spain Turkey	Ukraine	Bulgaria Croatia Spain Turkey	Great Britain Ukraine	Bulgaria Croatia Spain Turkey	Croatia	Bulgaria Croatia Spain Turkey	Great Britain Turkey Ukraine	Bulgaria Croatia Spain Turkey	Ukraine	Bulgaria Croatia Spain Turkey	Turkey Ukraine	Bulgaria Croatia Spain Turkey	Russia Ukraine

Notes: cross-country OLS estimates, bootstrapped standard errors (based on 1,000 replications) in parentheses. The dependent variable is per capita gross domestic product of 2016 (transformed by taking the natural logarithm; source: the World Bank). Model specifications in columns (2), (4), and (14) based on Cook’s distances.

^ p-value <0.1 * p-value <0.05 ** p-value <0.01 *** p-value <0.001

Table 1F. Cross-country variation in human development (robustness tests with selected countries omitted)

	HDI – 1	HDI – 2a	HDI – 2b	HDI – 3a	HDI – 3b	HDI – 4a	HDI – 4b	HDI – 5	HDI – 6a	HDI – 6b	HDI – 7a	HDI – 7b
Historical PI	-0.85*** -0.11	-0.75*** -0.21	-0.57*** -0.14	-0.84*** -0.14	-0.82*** -0.12	-0.43** -0.14	-0.46*** -0.08	-0.68*** -0.14	-0.36* -0.15	-0.36*** -0.1	-0.68*** -0.18	-0.74*** -0.15
Time Period	-0.06 -0.1	-0.14 -0.17	-0.25 -0.15	0.09 -0.09	0.06 -0.19	0 -0.1	0.13 -0.09	0 -0.09	0.08 -0.07	-0.1 -0.06	-0.09 -0.1	-0.08 -0.11
Historical GDP (ln)		0.13 -0.26	0.39 -0.25									
Neolithic Revolution				-0.16 -0.18	-0.09 -0.15							
CWI						0.52** -0.17	0.59*** -0.12					
Protestantism								0.27^ -0.16				
Communism									-0.57*** -0.16	-0.60*** -0.13		
State Antiquity											0.24 -0.19	0.19 -0.14
Intercept	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	22	22	23	20	23	22	25	22	22	25	22	24
Adj. R-squared	0.71	0.7	0.77	0.68	0.67	0.81	0.82	0.75	0.82	0.84	0.74	0.76
F-statistic	27.42***	17.66***	25.80***	14.76***	16.04***	30.79***	37.41***	21.72***	33.95***	42.99***	20.65***	25.50***
AIC	39.55	41.22	35.85	40.05	45.82	31.51	33.74	37.74	29.7	30.78	38.6	39.32
Omitted countries	Bulgaria Croatia Spain Turkey	Bulgaria Croatia Spain Turkey	Great Britain Norway	Bulgaria Croatia Spain Turkey	Turkey	Bulgaria Croatia Spain Turkey	Great Britain	Bulgaria Croatia Spain Turkey	Bulgaria Croatia Spain Turkey	Turkey	Bulgaria Croatia Spain Turkey	Turkey Ukraine

Notes: cross-country OLS estimates, bootstrapped standard errors (based on 1,000 replications) in parentheses. The dependent variable is Human Development Index of 2015 (source: United Nations Development Program (2016). Human development report 2016. New York, 198-201). Model specifications in columns (3), (5), (7), (10), and (12) based on Cook’s distances.

^ p-value <0.1 * p-value <0.05 ** p-value <0.01 *** p-value <0.001

Online Appendix: Section II*Table 2A.* Mosaic data files (as of December 2017)

Census	Regions	N (=pop.)
Mosaic data:		
Albania, 1918 census	8 rural regions, 6 cities	140,611
Austria-Hungary, 1869 census	9 rural regions from Hungary, Romania, Slovakia	31,406
Austria-Hungary, 1910 census	3 rural regions and 1 city from Austria	20,036
Belgium 1814 census	1 rural region from Western Flanders	13,666
Bulgaria, 1877-1947 household registers	1 rural region and 1 city from the Rhodope area	8,373
Dubrovnik, 1674 status animarum	1 rural region from Dalmatia	1,880
Denmark, 1803 census	9 rural regions and 2 urban regions from Schleswig and Holstein	107,861
France, 1846 census	3 rural regions	16,967
France, 1831-1901 census	1 rural region from South-Western France	5,109
France, 1846-1856 census	1 city from South-Western France	5,669
German Customs Union, 1846 census	10 rural regions and 4 urban regions	36,760
German Customs Union, 1858 census	1 rural region from the East	3,468
German Customs Union, 1861 census	1 rural region from the Southwest	6,541
German Customs Union, 1867 census	4 rural regions and 1 city in Mecklenburg-Schwerin	66,938
Germany, 1900 census	1 city	55,705
Mecklenburg-Schwerin, 1819 census	3 rural regions and 1 city	37,332
Münster, around 1700 status animarum	3 rural regions in North-Western Germany	23,010
Münster, 1749 status animarum	3 rural regions in North-Western Germany	34,169
Netherlands, census 1810-1811	2 rural regions and 3 cities in the south	40,037
Poland-Lithuania, 1768-1804 listings	12 rural regions	155,818
Poland-Lithuania, 1791-1792 census	3 urban regions	28,975
Moldavia, 1781-1879 status animarum	2 rural regions	5,291
Wallachia, 1838 census	4 rural regions	21,546

To be continued...

...Continuation from *Table 2A*

Census	Regions	N (=pop.)
Russia, 1710 enumeration	6 rural and 2 urban regions in the Ural area	27,736
Russia, 1765 census	4 rural regions in the Hetmanate area (Ukraine)	18,391
Russia, 1795 revision lists	1 rural region in Ukraine	8,050
Russia, 1797 revision lists	4 rural regions in Courland (Latvia)	35,807
Russia, 1814 private enumeration	1 region in Central Russia	2,955
Russia, 1847 enumeration	2 rural regions in Lithuania and Belarus	19,917
Russia, 1897 census	1 rural region around Moscow; 4 rural regions and 1 urban region around Berdychiv in Ukraine	34,441
Serbia, 1863 census	1 rural region and 1 city	9,746
Serbia, 1884 census	1 rural region	9,434
Spain, 1880-1890 local census	1 rural and 2 urban regions in Catalonia	23,997
Switzerland, 1671-1762 church listings	2 rural regions in canton Zürich	10,988
Switzerland, 1870 census	Zürich	8,152
Ottoman Empire, 1885 census	Istanbul	3,408
Ottoman Empire, 1907 census	Istanbul	4,946
<i>Mosaic data overall</i>	<i>142 regions (109 rural and 33 urban)</i>	<i>1,085,136</i>

Census	Regions	N (=pop.)
NAPP data		
Denmark, 1787 census (100%)	21 regions	838,623
Iceland, 1703 census (100%)	1 region	51,003
Norway, 1801 census (100%)	19 regions	878,073
Sweden, 1880 census (100%)	24 regions	4,624,825
United Kingdom, 1881 census:		
England (10% sample)	76 regions	2,926,374
Wales (10% sample)	13 regions	1,573,065
Scotland (10% sample)	32 regions	2,783,354
Islands (10% sample)	3 regions	139,614
<i>NAPP data overall</i>	<i>151 regions</i>	<i>14,252,150</i>

Online Appendix: Section III

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Mosaic Data

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